

Original Research

Screening of pesticide residues in a small agricultural watershed in Ogbomoso, Southwest Nigeria

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Abstract

Pesticide residues in soil and water along the Oba River watershed in Ogbomoso, southwest Nigeria, were investigated to assess environmental contamination from agricultural practices. Surface water and soil samples (36 each) were collected during the dry (December 2024) and wet (April 2024) seasons from six locations, including five agricultural sites (Ladokun, Iluju Maize Farms, Iluju Irrigation Scheme, Ikose Potatoes Farms, Vegetable Farms Iluju) and a control site (Yaku Ogbomoso). Samples were analysed using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) following the QuEChERS method. Semi-structured interviews with 55 farmers provided insights into pesticide use patterns. Results revealed significant contamination, with pesticide concentrations frequently exceeding the European Union Maximum Residue Limits (EU-MRL: 0.001- 0.01 mg/kg for soil, 0.1 mg/kg for water). In soil, Ladokun had the highest residues during the dry season, including Dichlorvos (1.52 ± 0.31 mg/kg), α -Lindane (1.35 ± 0.30 mg/kg), and Atrazine (1.27 ± 0.03 mg/kg). During the wet season, Ikose Potatoes Farms showed high levels of Chlorpyrifos (0.40 ± 0.08 mg/kg) and Dichlorvos (0.43 ± 0.12 mg/kg). In water, heptachlor peaked at Ladokun (2.13 ± 0.42 mg/kg) and Carbofuran at Ikose Potatoes Farms (2.13 ± 0.32 mg/kg) during the wet season. Organochlorines (Heptachlor, Dieldrin) and organophosphates (Chlorpyrifos, Dichlorvos) dominated, reflecting intensive pesticide use and persistence. The control site showed minimal residues, confirming agricultural activities as the primary contamination source. Farmers' limited knowledge of pesticide application, revealed through interviews, exacerbates environmental risks. These findings emphasise the need for sustainable agricultural practices, biopesticide adoption, and enhanced farmer education to mitigate ecological and health risks in the region.

Keywords

Pesticides, Agriculture, Residues, Chemicals, Environment, Surface, Soil, Water

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Preverjanje ostankov pesticidov v majhnem kmetijskem porečju v Ogbomосу v jugozahodni Nigeriji

Izvleček

Vzdolž porečja reke Oba v Ogbomосу, jugozahodna Nigerija, smo preiskali ostanke pesticidov v tleh in vodi, s čimer smo želeli oceniti onesnaženje okolja zaradi kmetijskih praks. Vzorec površinske vode in tal je bil odvzet med sušnim (december 2024) in deževnim (april 2024) obdobjem na šestih lokacijah, vključno s petimi kmetijskimi območji (Ladokun, Iluju Maize Farms, Iluju Irrigation Scheme, Ikose Potatoes Farms, Vegetable Farms Iluju) in kontrolnim območjem (Yaku Ogbomoso). Vzorci so bili analizirani z uporabo plinske kromatografije z masno spektrometrijo (GC-MS) po metodi QuEChERS. Polstrukturirani intervjuji z 55 kmeti so omogočili vpogled v vzorce uporabe pesticidov. Rezultati so pokazali znatno onesnaženost, saj so koncentracije pesticidov pogosto presegale najvišje dovoljene vrednosti ostankov Evropske unije (EU-MRL: 0,001–0,01 mg/kg za tla, 0,1 mg/kg za vodo). Najvišje ostanke v sušnem obdobju v tleh smo izmerili na lokaciji Ladokun: vključno z diklorvosom ($1,52 \pm 0,31$ mg/kg), α -lindanom ($1,35 \pm 0,30$ mg/kg) in atrazinom ($1,27 \pm 0,03$ mg/kg). V deževnem obdobju je kmetija Ikose Potatoes Farms pokazala visoke ravni klorpirifosa ($0,40 \pm 0,08$ mg/kg) in diklorvosa ($0,43 \pm 0,12$ mg/kg). V vodi je heptaklor dosegel najvišjo vrednost v Ladokunu ($2,13 \pm 0,42$ mg/kg), karbofuran pa na kmetiji Ikose Potatoes Farms ($2,13 \pm 0,32$ mg/kg) med deževnim obdobjem. Prevladovali so organoklorini (heptaklor, dieldrin) in organofosfati (klorpirifos, diklorvos), kar odraža intenzivno uporabo pesticidov in njihovo obstojnost. Na kontrolni lokaciji so bili ostanki minimalni, kar potrjuje, da so kmetijske dejavnosti glavni vir onesnaženja. Omejeno znanje kmetov o uporabi pesticidov, ki je bilo razvidno iz intervjujev, povečuje tveganja za okolje. Te ugotovitve poudarjajo potrebo po trajnostnih kmetijskih praksah, uvedbi biopesticidov in izboljšanju izobraževanja kmetov, da se zmanjšajo ekološka in zdravstvena tveganja v regiji.

Ključne besede

Pesticidi, kmetijstvo, ostanke, kemikalije, okolje, površina, tla, voda

Introduction

The intensification of agricultural and industrial activities worldwide has led to widespread contamination of natural resources, particularly soil and water, by pesticide residues and heavy metals, posing significant threats to ecosystems and human health (Han et al., 2025). Globally, pesticide consumption, encompassing herbicides, insecticides, and fungicides, reaches 2.0 to 3.5 million metric tons annually, with residues persisting in environmental compartments due to their chemical stability and mobility (Iqbal et al., 2025; Shah & Wu, 2019; Khan et al., 2023). Recent studies on hydrochemistry of the surface water in Oba River, Ogbomoso was investigated and revealed that there is need for regular monitoring of sodium content in the water to determine suitability for irrigation purpose (Ogungbesan et al., 2022), also It has been reported that freshwater contamination by pesticides is particularly acute, with surface water scores

exceeding thresholds in regions like Nigeria in Africa and South Asia, where over 50% of samples in many countries surpass regulatory limits for persistent compounds such as aldrin and dieldrin (Huang & Li, 2025). These residues show strong partitioning behaviours, with moderate to high soil organic carbon-water partition coefficients (Koc) facilitating long half-lives often exceeding 100 days, leading to bioaccumulation in soil microbiomes and aquatic systems, thereby threatening biodiversity, crop productivity, and public health through carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic pathways (Adesida et al., 2025; Lee et al., 2025).

Seasonal variations further exacerbate residue dynamics, as wet seasons dilute concentrations through dilution and runoff, while dry periods concentrate pollutants via reduced water volumes and intensified application (Commelin et al., 2022). In global agricultural hotspots, such as paddy fields and riverine systems, monitoring across seasons has detected up to 77% of targeted pesticides in soils

and 44% in waters exceeding safety thresholds (Lee et al., 2025). Land-use patterns amplify these effects, with arable lands showing elevated inputs compared to forested areas, influencing spatial distribution and degradation rates influenced by soil properties and organic matter (Jones and Brown, 2023; Lee et al., 2023).

In Africa, where agriculture underpins food security for over 60% of the population, pesticide reliance is acute amid climate variability and limited regulatory enforcement, resulting in hotspots of contamination (Osabohien, 2024). Countries like Malawi and Nigeria report extreme groundwater scores (up to 5.01) and non-carcinogenic health quotients exceeding 1, driven by runoff from intensive cropping (Huang & Li, 2025). Seasonal fluctuations are pronounced in semi-arid regions, such as Nigeria's Hadejia-Nguru wetlands, where dry-season concentrations of Dichlorvos (up to 231.70 µg/L) and permethrin (up to 80.00 µg/L in water; 197.95 mg/kg in sediments) far surpass wet-season levels, linked to heightened farming and low dilution (Adebayo et al., 2025). Similarly, in Katsina, Nigeria, agricultural sites, residues in water and soil spike during dry periods due to irrigation and dust mobilisation, underscoring the need for season-specific monitoring (Yusuf et al., 2025). These patterns reflect broader African trends, where land-use intensification in cultivated areas correlates with higher partitioning into aquatic-terrestrial interfaces, contrasting minimal inputs in non-arable systems (Corru, 2024; Degrendele et al., 2022).

The authors, García et al. (2024), recommended that for full elucidation on pesticides' fate, future research must address these multidimensional dynamics through integrated modelling approaches that couple land-use patterns, pesticide application regimes, and environmental variables. Such efforts are critical for developing sustainable agrochemical management strategies that minimise ecological risks while supporting agricultural productivity. In spite of this, screening of pesticides in environmental matrices such as soil and water has never been conducted on the Oba River sub-basin in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. Limited published studies have instead focused on vegetables and rice on the Oba River, severely limiting the possibility of targeted public-health interventions. This study then analysed surface water and soil samples collected during two seasons at 6 locations in a small agricultural watershed within the Oba River sub-basin in Ogbomoso for pesticides in order to identify pesticide use patterns within the watershed. In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted with the farmers along the river.

Materials and Methods

Sampling Area

The study was conducted in a small agricultural watershed within the Oba River sub-basin in Ogbomoso, southwestern Nigeria (Figure 1). An earthfill dam was built in 1964 across the river between Ikose and Yaku to provide Ogbomoso Township with potable water. Ogbomoso, southwest Nigeria, lies between 8° 00' N, 4° 10' E and 8° 15' N; 4° 20' E. According to Abegunrin et al. (2020), the region has an average of 1200 mm of rainfall annually, with mean annual minimum and maximum temperatures of 28 and 33°C, respectively. The bank of the river is usually grown to various crops (maize, okra, eggplant, etc.), especially during the dry season, when water is abstracted from the river (and the reservoir) with pumps for irrigation purposes.

Sampling

Samples were collected from six locations within the watershed in the Oba River sub-basin in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. The locations are: Ladokun Village (8.208591°N, 4.281720°E), Iluju Maize Farms (8.201696°N, 4.204226°E), Iluju Irrigation Farm (8.198282°N, 4.204270°E); Potatoes Farms within the Iluju Irrigation Scheme, the Vegetables Farm within Ikose Irrigation Scheme (8.188913°N, 4.199577°E). For comparative purposes, Yaku Village (8.178913°N, 4.199657°E) within the watershed was selected as the control site, representing an area with non-agricultural activities.

Soil samples were collected during the wet and dry seasons, after the crops had been planted at the locations. In all, 36 water and 36 soil samples were taken; 18 surface water and 18 soil samples were taken between April 6 and 14, 2024, during the rainy season, and 18 water and 18 soil samples were taken between December 15 and 20, 2024, during the dry season.

Water samples were collected in triplicate, using the manual grab method, at 15 - 60 cm depth. Most of the samples were taken 3 m (±1 m) away from the riverbank using a long-handled plastic dipper, and a subset of the samples was taken in the centre of the main flow. The sample bottles were washed with laboratory-grade soap and sterilised by immersion in a water bath for 10 minutes (Dastogeer, 2022). The bottles were rinsed several times with the water to be sampled before collection. Then, submerging and filling it to approximately 490 mL, the samples were imme-

added to the tube, and the sample was shaken vigorously for 10 min. Then, 4 g anhydrous MgSO₄ and 1 g NaCl were added to the tube, and the tube was shaken vigorously again for 5 min. Then the tubes were centrifuged for 5 min at a relative centrifugal force (RCF) of 2811 × g, and 1.5 mL supernatant was transferred into a 2 mL centrifuge tube containing 50 mg PSA and 150 mg MgSO₄. The 2 mL centrifuge tube was vortexed for 1 min and centrifuged for 5 min at RCF 2400 × g. Next, 1 mL supernatant was pipetted into a 2 mL centrifuge tube and the sample was dried by nitrogen flow in a water bath at 40 °C. Finally, 1 mL of ethyl acetate was added to the centrifuge tube to reconstitute the target pesticides, then the sample was passed through a 0.22 µm microporous membrane, and 10 µL IS was added into each vial for GC × GC-TOF-MS detection, which was performed using previously reported methods (K. Wang et al., 2023) and described in the Supporting Information. For water samples, 100 mL of water samples was pipetted into a triangular flask, and the pH of the water samples was adjusted between 3 and 5 with HCl. Before loading samples, a sequential solid-phase extraction (SSPE) cartridge, a C18 cartridge (on top) coupled with an HLB cartridge (on bottom), was activated by 5 mL of acetone, methanol, and ultra-pure water in sequence. After that, 100 mL water samples were passed through the SSPE cartridge and were dried under a vacuum for 15 min to remove retained water. The C18 cartridge and HLB cartridge were eluted 3 times using 15 mL of acetone and DCM (4:1, v/v), and the eluent was collected. Next, the eluent was evaporated to dry by using a rotary evaporator (40 °C, 0.09 MPa). The next steps of sample preparation and injection were the same as in the above-mentioned description

Gas Chromatography Analysis

The samples were analysed using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) using a Varian 3800/4000 system for the pesticide residues identification and quantification. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a capillary column AT-1, length was 30 m, ID was 0.25 mm, and film thickness was 0.25 µm. The carrier gas was nitrogen (purity 99.00%) supplied at a constant flow rate of 1.5 mL/min. The GC oven was programmed with an initial temperature of 70 °C held for 2 min, then rose to 300 °C at the rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ and held again for 7 min. The total run time was 32.0 minutes. The GC-MS interface temperature was at 280 °C. Injector and detector temperatures were set

at 250 °C. Flow control mode was set to linear velocity. 1 µL of sample was injected in a split ratio of 30:0. The Mass Spectrometer was operated with a scan range of 40-800 Da. Suspected pesticide compounds were identified by comparing their retention times in sample chromatograms to those of the corresponding pure analytical standards, along with data from an established compound library. The quantities of detected compounds were expressed as relative area percentages, as calculated by the system integrator.

Mafura (2024) pointed out that the limit of detection (LOD) of GC-MS equipment used for each pesticide was determined by running an air blank sample under the experimental conditions to obtain the detector baseline noise. A detectable ion should produce a signal that is at least three times the baseline noise. Individual pesticide LOD was estimated by serially running diluted solutions of the pesticide standard and recording the baseline noise ratio (signal-to-noise = 3).

The analysis was conducted at Afe Babalola University's Chemical Engineering Laboratory in Ado Ekiti, Nigeria.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics such as mean, range, and standard error were used to analyse the data using SAS software version 9.2 (SAS Institute, 2005). Additionally, pesticide residue levels from the six locations were statistically evaluated using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and mean differences were determined through Duncan's Multiple Range Test at a 5% significance level.

Quality assurance procedures

Quality assurance procedures were implemented to ascertain that the analytical methods rigorously adhered to standards and specifications. Additionally, these measures helped guarantee that the results evaluated were valuable, valid, and of high standard, including the assessment of recovery rate and detection limits.

Semi-Structured Interviews

A semi-structured interview is a technique for gathering data in which questions are arranged according to a pre-defined thematic framework but are not presented in terms of sequence or wording (Price et al., 2021). An interview

was conducted for fifty-five farmers who own farms along the Oba River, where soil and water samples were taken at each of the six locations. Semi-structured interviews using oral interviews were used to gather information from the informants regarding the history of the Oba River, the kinds of pesticides they use, how long they spray them for, when they harvest their produce, and how many years they have been involved in applying pesticides. Identification of pesticide-related products and the language on pesticide package labels was also conducted during the interviews and field observations.

Results and Discussion

Soil

The analysis of pesticide residues in soil samples collected during the dry and wet seasons from various locations (Ladokun village, Iluju Maize Farms, Iluju Irrigation Farms, Ikose Potatoes farms, Vegetable farms Iluju, and Yaku Ogbomoso (Control) revealed significant variations in pesticide concentrations across the locations, as presented in Tables 4.1 and 4.2. The concentrations of pesticide residues, expressed in mg/kg, were compared against the European Union Maximum Residue Limit (EU-MRL) for soil (0.001 - 0.01 mg/kg). In Table 4.1, Ladokun showed the highest concentrations for most pesticides, including Dichlorvos (1.52 ± 0.31 mg/kg), α -Lindane (1.35 ± 0.30 mg/kg), Atrazine (1.27 ± 0.03 mg/kg), γ -Lindane (1.19 ± 0.26 mg/kg), and Dieldrin (1.09 ± 0.25 mg/kg), ($P = 0.038$). These levels significantly exceeded the EU-MRL, indicating potential contamination risks. Other locations, such as Iluju maize farms, Iluju Irrigation Farms, Ikose Potatoes farms and Vegetable farms Iluju showed lower concentrations, generally ranging from 0.07 to 0.56 mg/kg, though still above the EU-MRL for most pesticides. The control location (Yaku Ogbomoso) consistently recorded the lowest concentrations, often at or below detection limits (0.00 ± 0.00 mg/kg for α -Lindane, Atrazine, and γ -Lindane), serving as a baseline for uncontaminated soil, however pesticides like Heptachlor, Carbofuran, and Carbaryl were absent or present in trace amounts (0.00 ± 0.00 mg/kg) at the control site, while other locations showed detectable levels. For instance, Heptachlor concentrations reached 0.56 ± 0.12 mg/kg at Iluju maize farms and 0.55 ± 0.11 mg/kg ($P = 0.40$) at Iluju Irrigation farms, indicating significant contamination at these agricultural areas.

Table 4.2 further highlighted the persistence of pesticide residues in wet seasons, with Chlorpyrifos, Dichlorvos, and Endosulfan showing highest concentrations at Ikose potatoes farms (0.40 ± 0.08 mg/kg, 0.43 ± 0.12 mg/kg, and 0.32 ± 0.08 ($P = 0.36$) mg/kg, respectively) and Vegetable farms Iliju (0.35 ± 0.06 mg/kg for Endosulfan). The control site again showed minimal or no detectable residues for most pesticides, reinforcing its role as a reference for uncontaminated soil. The results indicate that all tested locations, except the control, exceeded the EU-MRL for multiple pesticides, with Ladokun consistently showing the highest contamination levels. The presence of organochlorines (Dieldrin, p,p'-DDT, α -Lindane) and organophosphates (Chlorpyrifos, Malathion) at elevated levels suggests intensive pesticide use in these agricultural areas. The higher pesticide residue levels observed in the soil samples from all locations except the control site reflect intensive agricultural practices and the persistent nature of certain pesticides, such as organochlorines and organophosphates. The significantly higher concentrations at Ladokun compared to other location may be attributed to its proximity to intensive farming activities or historical pesticide use, which aligns with findings by Iwegbue et al. (2020), who reported organochlorine residues in soils from Nigerian agricultural regions due to prolonged application and slow degradation rates also Adesina et al. (2024) detected a total of eight organochlorine pesticide residues in soil samples collected in selected arable farms in the Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State. Numerous nonexclusive factors related to environmental conditions, type of crop studied, agronomic practices, and pesticide properties, as well as sampling time (e.g., date since last application), sampling strategies, and analytical methods (e.g., limits of detection and quantification), may drive the differences observed between the present results and the previous studies (Bonmatin et al., 2015; Pelosi et al., 2021). The control site's minimal residue levels confirm that non-agricultural soils are less likely to accumulate pesticide residues, consistent with studies by Akan et al. (2015), who found negligible pesticide levels in undisturbed soils. The detection of organochlorines like Dieldrin, α -Lindane, and p,p'-DDT at concentrations far exceeding the EU-MRL (0.001 - 0.01 mg/kg) raises concerns about their environmental persistence and potential bioaccumulation. Organochlorines are known for their long half-lives and resistance to degradation, as noted by Jayaraj et al. (2016), who highlighted their ability to persist

in soils for decades, posing risks to soil ecosystems and human health through food chain contamination. The presence of organophosphates such as Chlorpyrifos and Malathion, though less persistent, indicates recent pesticide application, as these compounds typically degrade faster than organochlorines (Aktar et al., 2009). However, the residue levels in this study are higher than those reported in some recent studies from other regions. For instance, Liu et al. (2025) found lower concentrations of Dichlorvos (0.01–0.05 mg/kg) in Chinese agricultural soils, suggesting differences in pesticide regulation or application practices. Similarly, Silva et al. (2019) reported Atrazine levels below 0.1 mg/kg in European soils, contrasting with the 0.05–1.27 mg/kg observed here. These discrepancies may reflect stricter regulatory frameworks in Europe compared to less regulated pesticide use in the study area. The variation in pesticide concentrations across locations (e.g. higher levels at Ladokun and Ikose Potato farm compared to

vegetable farms Iluju) suggests site-specific factors, such as type of crop cultivated, soil type, organic matter content, or irrigation practices, influencing residue retention. This is supported by Mahmoud et al. (2022), who found that soil organic matter enhances the adsorption of pesticides like Atrazine, reducing their mobility but increasing persistence. The higher residue levels at the irrigated site may also indicate leaching or runoff from nearby fields, a phenomenon described by Adimassu et al. (2019).

Water

The data from Tables 4.3 and 4.4 present the concentrations of pesticide residues in water samples collected during the dry and wet seasons across various locations along the Oba River in Ogbomoso, Nigeria, including Ladokun, Iluju Maize Farms (ILJ Maize), Iluju Irrigation Scheme (ILJ IRGN), Ikose Potatoes Farms (IPF), Vegetable Farms (VFI), and Control.

Table 1. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in soil along the Oba River during the dry season.

Tabela 1. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v tleh ob reki Oba med sušnim obdobjem.

Pesticides	Ladokun	Locations				
		ILJ Maize	ILJ IRGN	IPF	VFI	Control
Dichlorvos	1.52 ^a ±0.31	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.28 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.16 ^d ±0.06	0.33 ^b ±0.02	0.02 ^e ±0.00
a-Lindane	1.35 ^a ±0.30	0.27 ^b ±0.06	0.23 ^c ±0.06	0.21 ^{cd} ±0.05	0.22 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Atrazine	1.27 ^a ±0.03	0.14 ^{cd} ±0.02	0.15 ^c ±0.04	0.17 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.23 ^b ±0.03	0.00 ^e ±0.00
γ-Lindane	1.19 ^a ±0.26	0.31 ^b ±0.08	0.33 ^b ±0.09	0.30 ^{cb} ±0.07	0.25 ^c ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Dieldrin	1.09 ^a ±0.25	0.17 ^c ±0.3	0.14 ^{dc} ±0.04	0.28 ^b ±0.06	0.15 ^{cd} ±0.04	0.00 ^e ±0.00
p,p'-DDT	0.64 ^a ±0.15	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.34 ^b ±0.12	0.21 ^{cd} ±0.04	0.15 ^d ±0.03	0.06 ^e ±0.00
β-HCH	0.53 ^a ±0.12	0.41 ^{ab} ±0.09	0.40 ^{ab} ±0.09	0.35 ^b ±0.07	0.27 ^c ±0.10	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Chlorpyrifos	0.51 ^a ±0.07	0.31 ^b ±0.06	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.25 ^{bcd} ±0.05	0.28 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Aldrin	0.36 ^a ±0.06	0.07 ^d ±0.01	0.09 ^{cd} ±0.02	0.20 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.07 ^d ±0.03	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Methomyl	0.23 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.27 ^a ±0.06	0.22 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.21 ^{bcd} ±0.02	0.17 ^d ±0.03	0.00 ^b ±0.00
Heptachlor epoxide	0.17 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.28 ^{ab} ±0.07	0.27 ^b ±0.06	0.29 ^a ±0.06	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Malathion	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.01	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.04	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.04	0.17 ^a ±0.03	0.10 ^c ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Carbaryl	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.27 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.28 ^a ±0.07	0.22 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.26 ^b ±0.04	0.18 ^{cd} ±0.00
Carbofuran	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.21 ^a ±0.3	0.16 ^b ±0.03	0.12 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.12 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Heptachlor	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.56 ^a ±0.12	0.55 ^a ±0.11	0.50 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.18 ^b ±0.03	0.04 ^c ±0.02

Means with the same superscript(s) are not significantly different along the column at 5% probability ($p > 0.05$). European Union Maximum Residue Limit for Soil: 0.001–0.01

Locations: Ladokun Ogbomoso, ILJ: Iluju Maize Farms, ILJ IRGN: Iluju Irrigation Scheme, IPF: Ikose Potatoes Farms, VFI: Vegetable Farms Iluju, Control: Yaku Ogbomoso

Table 2. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in soil along the Oba River during the wet season.

Tabela 2. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v tleh ob reki Oba med deževnim obdobjem.

Pesticides	Ladokun	Locations				
		ILJ Maize	ILJ IRGN	IPF	VFI	Control
Chlorpyrifos	0.18 ^{bc} ±0.07	0.18 ^{bc} ±0.00	0.40 ^a ±0.10	0.40 ^a ±0.08	0.22 ^b ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Malathion	0.16 ^{ab} ±0.02	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.24 ^a ±0.8	0.24 ^a ±0.3	0.07 ^{ab} ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Carbaryl	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.27 ^a ±0.08	0.26 ^{ab} ±0.6	0.12 ^c ±0.04	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Cypermethrin	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.15 ^b ±0.08	0.12 ^c ±0.02	0.10 ^{cd} ±0.02	0.28 ^a ±0.08	0.04 ^d ±0.00
Dichlorvos	0.13 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.24 ^a ±0.04	0.43 ^a ±0.12	0.43 ^a ±0.12	0.33 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Aldrin	0.11 ^{ad} ±0.06	0.04 ^d ±0.02	0.21 ^{ab} ±0.5	0.24 ^a ±0.05	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Atrazine	0.05 ^{cd} ±0.04	0.23 ^c ±0.05	0.25 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.30 ^a ±0.06	0.27 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.09 ^c ±0.02
Endosulfan	0.04 ^{cde} ±0.01	0.06 ^{de} ±0.02	0.31 ^b ±0.08	0.32 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.35 ^a ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Heptachlor	0.03 ^c ±0.01	0.03 ^{bc} ±0.001	0.27 ^a ±0.05	0.27 ^a ±0.10	0.06 ^b ±0.01	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Phosphoric acid	0.03 ^c ±0.02	0.09 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.19 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.20 ^a ±0.08	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Carbofuran	0.03 ^{cd} ±0.01	0.17 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.14 ^{bcf} ±0.06	0.16 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.23 ^a ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Dieldrin	0.02 ^{de} ±0.01	0.09 ^{cd} ±0.04	0.08 ^e ±0.002	0.07 ^{ef} ±0.03	0.03 ^{ef} ±0.01	0.00 ^d ±0.00
γ-Lindane	0.01 ^{de} ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Chlorthiophos	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.04 ^{de} ±0.02	0.25 ^{ade} ±0.04	0.24 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.24 ^{abcd} ±0.0	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Methomyl	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.008	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.23 ^a ±0.06	0.21 ^{ab} ±0.04	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Chlordan	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.006	0.30 ^a ±0.06	0.30 ^a ±0.06	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00
Prothiofos	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.32 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.32 ^{abc} ±0.08	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00
a-Lindane	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.00 ^e ±0.00	0.13 ^{cdef} ±0.6	0.15 ^{cdef} ±0.05	0.07 ^{def} ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
p,p'-DDT	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.17 ^a ±0.04	0.17 ^a ±0.05	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.05 ^c ±0.01

Key: Means with the same superscript(s) are not significantly different along the column at 5% probability ($p > 0.05$). European Union Maximum Residue Limit for Soil: 0.001- 0.01

Locations: Ladokun Ogbomoso, ILJ: Iluju Maize Farms, ILJ IRGN: Iluju Irrigation Scheme, IPF: Ikose Potatoes Farms, VFI: Vegetable Farms Iluju, Control: Yaku Ogbomoso

Iluju (VFI), and a control site (Yaku Ogbomoso). In Table 4.3, during the dry season, heptachlor had the highest concentration at Ladokun (0.64 ± 0.31 mg/kg), significantly higher than the control (0.04 ± 0.01 mg/kg) ($P = 0.46$). β -HCH concentrations ranged from 0.33 ± 0.09 mg/kg (VFI) to 0.50 ± 0.10 mg/kg (ILJ IRGN), with the control showing no detectable residues. Other pesticides, such as γ -Lindane, Dichlorvos, Chlorpyrifos, and Carbaryl, showed concentrations significantly above the control across most locations, with values ranging from 0.15 ± 0.03 mg/kg (Malathion at VFI) to 0.33 ± 0.09 mg/kg (γ -Lindane at Ladokun and Iluju Irrigation Scheme). Table 4.4, during wet season Heptachlor concentrations peaked at Ladokun (2.13 ± 0.42 mg/kg),

significantly higher than other locations, where it was often undetectable, Carbofuran showed a high concentration at Ikose Potatoes farms (2.13 ± 0.32 mg/kg), while Chlordan and p,p'-DDT were notably high at Iluju Maize farms (1.48 ± 0.06 mg/kg and 1.30 ± 0.14 mg/kg, ($P = 0.30$) respectively). Atrazine and Dieldrin also showed higher levels, with maximum concentrations of 0.36 ± 0.08 mg/kg (ILJ Maize) and 1.11 ± 0.16 mg/kg (IPF), respectively. These findings are in alignment with several studies that have investigated the residue of pesticides in water, for instance, Ng et al. 2023; Ngin et al. 2024). Ngin et al. (2024) detected a total of 56 out of the 64 pesticides in the 96 surface-water samples, with average concentrations for individual pesticides

ranging from 0.05 to 1300 ng/L. Ng et al. (2023) focused on 2362 contaminants, and 586 pesticides were detected up to a maximum concentration of 1171 ng/L in the Danube River Basin, Europe's second largest river basin, also pesticide concentrations found in this present study were similar to those found by Awe et al. (2022) in a study conducted in Atakumosa West Local Government, Osun State. In their study, they found pesticide residues in the water, including dimethoate, pirimiphos-methyl, prothiofos, pyrazophos, dementon-s-methyl, profenofos, malathion, and omethoate, with amounts ranging from 0.06 to 6.11 mg/L. The results indicate widespread pesticide contamination in water samples from agricultural sites in Ogbomoso, with concentrations consistently exceeding the EU-MRL for soil (0.001-0.01 mg/kg). This suggests potential environmental and health risks, as water is a critical medium for pesticide transport and human exposure. Heptachlor, a persistent organochlorine pesticide, showed particularly high levels

at Ladokun, consistent with its historical use and persistence in the environment (Olisah et al., 2020). Similarly, Higher levels of Carbofuran and Dieldrin at Ikose Potatoes farm and Iluju Maize farms align with their intensive use in agriculture, as noted in studies on pesticide residues in African water systems (Olisah et al., 2020). The absence or low levels of residues at the control site (Yaku Ogbomoso) confirm that agricultural activities are the primary source of contamination. However, recent studies report similar trends. For instance, Olisah (2020) found organochlorine residues in Ghanaian water bodies exceeding international standards, attributing this to agricultural runoff. Akan et al. (2015) reported high levels of DDT and Lindane in Nigerian water systems, corroborating the elevated p,p'-DDT and γ -Lindane concentrations observed here. The high variability in residue levels across locations may reflect differences in pesticide application practices, soil types, or irrigation methods, as suggested by Iniaghe et al. (2022).

Table 3. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in water along the Oba River during the dry season.

Tabela 3. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v vodi vzdolž reke Oba med sušnim obdobjem.

Pesticides	Ladokun	Locations				
		ILJ Maize	ILJ IRGN	IPF	VFI	Control
Heptachlor	0.64 ^a ±0.31	0.56 ^{ab} ±0.12	0.55 ^b ±0.8	0.49 ^{bc} ±0.011	0.16 ^c ±0.04	0.04 ^d ±0.01
β -HCH	0.43 ^b ±0.09	0.45 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.50 ^a ±0.10	0.37 ^b ±0.07	0.33 ^{bc} ±0.09	0.00 ^d ±0.00
γ -Lindane	0.33 ^a ±0.09	0.32 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.33 ^a ±0.09	0.30 ^b ±0.07	0.25 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.04 ^c ±0.02
Dichlorvos	0.28 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.26 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.28 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.16 ^b ±0.03	0.30 ^a ±0.05	0.01 ^c ±0.00
Chlorpyrifos	0.27 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.31 ^a ±0.09	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.08	0.25 ^c ±0.05	0.27 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Heptachlor epoxide	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.28 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.27 ^b ±0.06	0.29 ^a ±0.06	0.16 ^{cd} ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Carbaryl	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.08	0.27 ^b ±0.07	0.28 ^a ±0.08	0.22 ^c ±0.00	0.26 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.08 ^d ±0.04
Dieldrin	0.23 ^{ab} ±0.03	0.23 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.26 ^a ±0.06	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Methomyl	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.27 ^a ±0.05	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.21 ^b ±0.05	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.08 ^c ±0.04
α -Lindane	0.20 ^{bc} ±0.05	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.08	0.23 ^a ±0.06	0.21 ^b ±0.08	0.22 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
p,p'-DDT	0.18 ^b ±0.05	0.25 ^a ±0.06	0.16 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.21 ^{ab} ±0.06	0.15 ^c ±0.05	0.05 ^d ±0.01
Malathion	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.03	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.03	0.15 ^{ab} ±0.2	0.17 ^a ±0.03	0.11 ^b ±0.03	0.00 ^c ±0.00
Carbofuran	0.15 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.21 ^a ±0.05	0.16 ^b ±0.04	0.12 ^c ±0.05	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.00 ^b ±0.00
Aldrin	0.11 ^b ±0.03	0.07 ^{bc} ±0.03	0.08 ^{bc} ±0.7	0.07 ^c ±0.04	0.27 ^a ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Atrazine	0.11 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.15 ^b ±0.05	0.13 ^b ±0.05	0.18 ^{ab} ±0.04	0.22 ^a ±0.04	0.00 ^d ±0.00

Key: Means with the same superscript(s) are not significantly different along the column at 5% probability ($p > 0.05$). European Union Maximum Residue Limit for Soil: 0.001-0.01

Locations: L1: Ladokun Ogbomoso, ILJ: Iluju Maize Farms, ILJ IRGN: Iluju Irrigation Scheme, IPF: Ikose Potatoes Farms, VFI: Vegetable Farms Iluju, Control: Yaku Ogbomoso

Table 4. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in water along the Oba River during the wet season.

Tabela 4. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v vodi vzdolž reke Oba med deževnim obdobjem.

Pesticides	Ladokun	Locations				
		ILJ Maize	ILJ IRGN	IPF	VFI	Control
Heptachlor	2.13 ^a ±0.42	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.22 ^b ±0.06	0.00 ^f ±0.00	0.17 ^c ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Endosulfan	0.19 ^b ±0.04	0.01 ^d ±0.00	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.22 ^a ±0.07	0.10 ^c ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Atrazine	0.17 ^b ±0.04	0.36 ^a ±0.08	0.08 ^c ±0.06	0.02 ^d ±0.01	0.16 ^{bc} ±0.08	0.01 ^e ±0.00
Dichlorvos	0.14 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.04 ^e ±0.02	0.02 ^c ±0.01	0.24 ^b ±0.08	0.34 ^a ±0.07	0.02 ^b ±0.00
Carbaryl	0.11 ^b ±0.03	0.10 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.01 ^d ±0.00	0.13 ^a ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Dieldrin	0.10 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.07 ^c ±0.03	0.08 ^{bc} ±0.02	1.11 ^a ±0.16	0.21 ^b ±0.06	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Chlorpyrifos	0.08 ^b ±0.02	0.03 ^c ±0.01	0.07 ^{bc} ±0.04	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.21 ^a ±0.08	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Malathion	0.08 ^{bc} ±0.06	0.08 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.45 ^a ±0.10	0.24 ^b ±0.06	0.05 ^c ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Aldrin	0.05 ^{bc} ±0.01	1.42 ^a ±0.14	1.28 ^{ab} ±0.21	0.16 ^b ±0.07	0.05 ^{bc} ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00
a-Lindane	0.04 ^d ±0.02	1.28 ^a ±0.16	0.03 ^c ±0.00	0.83 ^b ±0.20	0.14 ^c ±0.04	0.00 ^a ±0.00
Cypermethrin	0.02 ^a ±0.01	0.00 ^b ±0.00	0.01 ^{ab} ±0.00	0.01 ^b ±0.00	0.01 ^b ±0.00	0.00 ^b ±0.00
Chlorthiophos	0.02 ^b ±0.01	0.01 ^c ±0.00	0.02 ^c ±0.01	0.01 ^c ±0.00	0.07 ^a ±0.02	0.00 ^c ±0.00
Carbofuran	0.02 ^{bc} ±0.01	0.01 ^c ±0.00	0.06 ^b ±0.02	2.13 ^a ±0.32	0.03 ^c ±0.01	0.00 ^d ±0.00
Methomyl	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.22 ^a ±0.08	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.00 ^c ±0.00	0.11 ^b ±0.05	0.00 ^c ±0.00
Chlordan	0.00 ^d ±0.00	1.48 ^a ±0.06	0.53 ^b ±0.09	0.04 ^c ±0.01	0.07 ^c ±0.05	0.00 ^d ±0.00
p,p'-DDT	0.00 ^d ±0.00	1.30 ^a ±0.14	0.03 ^c ±0.01	0.04 ^{bc} ±0.01	0.11 ^b ±0.06	0.05 ^{bc} ±0.02
β-HCH	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.09 ^a ±0.04	0.02 ^c ±0.00	0.04 ^b ±0.02	0.00 ^d ±0.00	0.00 ^c ±0.00

Key: Means with the same superscript(s) are not significantly different along the column at 5% probability ($p > 0.05$). European Union Maximum Residue Limit for Soil: 0.001- 0.01

Locations: L1: Ladokun Ogbomoso, ILJ: Iluju Maize Farms, ILJ IRGN: Iluju Irrigation Scheme, IPF: Ikose Potatoes Farms, VFI: Vegetable Farms Iluju, Control: Yaku Ogbomoso

Soil and Water

There are higher concentrations of pesticides in water than in soil. The reduced quantity of pesticides found in the soil aligns with the findings of Manjarres-López et al. (2021), who reported that over fifty per cent of the sampled pesticides were undetected in the soil. The impact of soil properties on the remaining levels of pesticide is anticipated, given that the adsorption process by both organic and inorganic soil components may increase the longevity of these substances. Indeed, several studies in the literature indicate the impact of organic matter and clay content on the adsorption, degradation, and persistence of certain compounds found in soils (Marín-Benito et al., 2017; Sadegh et al., 2017). The significant quantity of compounds

identified in certain water samples may be attributed to the application of various pesticides employed for managing pests in crops or vineyards near water sources, or possibly due to the reduced distance between the fields and the water source (Schreiner et al., 2016). The elevated levels of these compounds found in water samples indicate that their presence may be attributed to their consistent use across various seasons. Point-source contamination may also account for these elevated concentrations, as suggested by other researchers (Bagheri et al., 2023).

Based on the total sum of average concentrations of all pesticides for both seasons. The pesticides with the highest concentrations in both water and soil samples are heptachlor, Dichlorvos, aldrin, atrazine, and carbofuran, which have values of 4.96, 4.13, 3.56, 3.15, and 3.03 mg/kg,

respectively. This conclusion suggests that farmers in the area frequently utilise these chemical compounds, which can be inferred from the types of crops cultivated in the region (Demi et al., 2021). However, the study reveals that insect pests most frequently target vegetables, maize, cowpeas, and millet as their dominant crops. In addition to this, the farmers in this study area utilise herbicides for weed control, which have been the primary source of the observed residues in both soil and water (Nath et al., 2024).

There are more organochlorines (11) than other chemical groups in the present study. This aligns with the findings of Zhang et al. (2022), who observed several residual levels of organochlorine in samples collected during the rainy season. Increased drainage and disturbances in the water column during rainfall may cause this phenomenon. Organochlorine pesticides exhibit prolonged residual effects and remain in the environment for extended durations while maintaining their toxicity (Ren et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2025; Faraj et al., 2024). Meanwhile, the concentration of organophosphate

compound residues in soil samples was consistently higher than that in water samples, aligning with the findings of Awe et al. (2022). This result is expected because the pesticides are applied directly to the crops and soil, so their levels are likely to decrease due to their tendency to evaporate before they wash into nearby water sources.

Figure 2 revealed the comparison between the two major class of pesticides used in the study area was presented in the bar chart. The result shows that the highest percentage of pesticides used in the study area is Insecticides, which constitute 94% percent followed by Herbicides, which had 6%. This indicates that the use of insecticides to control the insect pests against the attack on Agricultural commodities in the study area is very common, and the rate of using herbicides is also high, and this might be due to frequent control of weeds, especially during the rainy season. This study is in line with Rousis et al. (2017), who reported that insecticides are the major pesticide used in agriculture and also in the household to control insects.

Figure 2. Level of major pesticide detected in soil samples from the study area.

Slika 2. Raven glavnih pesticidov, ugotovljena v vzorcih tal iz območja študije.

Environmental risk assessment

Most of the concentration of the pesticides found in the present study exceeded the maximum residue levels (MRLs) set for pesticides in water, 0.1 mg/kg (Olawale et al., 2022). The least concentration of each individual pesticide found was 0.01 mg/kg. This finding implies that environmentalists and scientists should conduct public education about pesticides for rural farmers who have little knowledge about the MRLs for pesticides. However, the total pesticide concentration could not be considered for evaluating the level of soil contamination because there is no EU legislation establishing thresholds or quality standards for total or individual pesticide residues in the soil, even though this subject should be addressed in the characterisation of overall soil quality (Silva et al., 2019).

Semi-structured interviews

All the respondents who were surveyed reported using pesticides. However, due to either inadequate labelling or other factors, none of them were informed about the active chemicals present in the pesticide products they utilised. The analysis successfully identified unique products containing the same active ingredients through a visual examination of the pesticides used by the inter-

viewed farmers and the pesticide containers observed at the sampling locations. The farmers report the practice of frequently mixing various pesticide products in spray tanks and applying this combination without considering the specific types of pesticides involved. This finding is consistent with previous investigations that evaluated the actual circumstances of pesticide application among Cambodian farmers in rural regions (Matsukawa et al., 2016). Information regarding the appropriate amounts to be used and the timing between application and harvest was obtained from neighbours and pesticide vendors. Pesticides are utilised to control diseases and prevent pests from damaging crops, as outlined in the description. It was found that a significant portion of farmers, specifically two-thirds, lack awareness regarding the application of pesticides. This could be the situation, as numerous individuals approach circumstances through the lens of their personal experiences and may lack knowledge regarding the proper application of pesticides. While the extensive experience of farmers is essential for managing pesticides, a professional understanding is required for the safe handling of these substances. A number of the farmers surveyed indicated that they resort to using an alternative pesticide the following day if the initial application fails to prevent insect damage to their crops, which may contribute to the accumulation of pesticides in the environment.

Table 5. Concentration (mg/kg) of pesticide residues in water along the Oba River during the wet season.

Tabela 5. Koncentracija (mg/kg) ostankov pesticidov v vodi vzdolž reke Oba med deževnim obdobjem.

Pesticide	Types	
	Type of the Pesticide	Trade Name
Profenofos at 40% + Cypermethrin at 4%	Insecticide	Sharp Shooter, Rocket Termite Killer, Ironforce.
Captan	Fungicide	Tepuca. Agrox, Captal, Captec, Captol, Captonex, Clomitane, Merpan, Meteoro
Dichlorvos	Insecticide	DD force, Daksh, DDVP, Snipper, Dede vap, Nogos, Task, No pest, crush
Diquat Chloride	Herbicide	FieldKlear, Reglone, Reward, Aquacide, Weedtrine-D, Dextrone, and Preeglone
Cypermethrin	Insecticide	CypeForce, Cyper-DiForce, and Sharp Shooter
Emamectin Benzoate	Insecticide	Caterpillar Force, allakat, DPRO, FAMEN B, Lepto
Lambda-Cyhalothrin	Insecticide	Lara Force, Karate
Mancozeb	Fungicide	Z-Force fungicide, Quintozen, Zebshi
Abamectin	Antiparasitic agent	Abamet, Punch, Trustil
Profenofos	Insecticide	Dominator. Sharp Shooter, Dominator, and DD Force
Atrazine	Insecticide	Atraforce, AtranexMazine Atraz

Source: Field Survey 2024.

Conclusion

This study provides critical insights into the extent of pesticide contamination in soil and water along the Oba River in Ogbomoso, Nigeria, highlighting the pervasive impact of agricultural practices on environmental quality. The analysis of 36 soil and 36 surface water samples collected during the dry and wet seasons from six locations revealed significant pesticide residues, with concentrations frequently exceeding the European Union Maximum Residue Limits (EU-MRL) of 0.001 - 0.01 mg/kg for soil and 0.1 mg/kg for water. Organochlorines (Heptachlor, Dieldrin, α -Lindane, p,p'-DDT) and organophosphates (Chlorpyrifos, Dichlorvos) were the dominant contaminants, with Ladokun and Ikose Potatoes Farms exhibiting the highest concentrations, particularly during the wet season. The control site (Yaku Village) consistently showed minimal or no detectable residues, showing the role of intensive agricultural activities as the primary source of contamination. Seasonal variations were evident, with higher pesticide levels in both soil and water during the wet season, likely due to increased application rates and runoff facilitated by heavy rainfall. The semi-structured interviews with 55 farmers revealed widespread pesticide use, often without adequate knowledge of active ingredients, application rates, or safety protocols, contributing to environmental accumulation. The elevated pesticide levels in water compared to soil suggest significant transport via runoff, posing risks to aquatic ecosystems and human health through potential food chain contamination. It is essential to adopt sustainable agricultural practices that encompass conservation tillage, ecological ditches, and biological weed removal. Additionally, educating farmers about the use of pesticides during land clearing and their effects on water bodies and crops is crucial. Natural pesticides, often referred

to as biopesticides, are strongly advocated as a viable alternative to synthetic pesticides, particularly in the context of ensuring food security and promoting environmental sustainability. Additional investigations are necessary to encompass a broader range of local government areas and agricultural settlements within the state. It is essential for the government to contemplate the allocation of funds for studies of this nature, as the data gathered can significantly contribute to the development and refinement of policies.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, O.J. and O.A.; methodology, T.P. and O.A.; software, E.O. and K.A.; validation, O.J. and O.A.; formal analysis, O.J. and O.A.; investigation, T.P.; resources, O.A.; data curation, O.J. and E.O.; writing original draft preparation, O.J.; writing review and editing, O.J. and O.A.; visualization, T.P. and K.A.; supervision, O.A. and T.P.; project administration, O.A. and O.J.; funding acquisition, O.J. and O.A. We confirm that the manuscript has been read and approved by all named authors and that there are no other persons who satisfied the criteria for authorship

Declaration of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

Research data tables were deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17614950>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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